

NSF GEO REU Program Coordinators Show Adaptability and Resiliency During the Pandemic

Jenna A. Lamphere

Assistant Professor, Texas A&M University, Galveston

Valerie F. Sloan

Director of GEO REU Network and Early Career Professional Development Lead for Atmospheric Research, National Center for Atmospheric Research

Marissa Palmer

Graduate Research Assistant, Texas A&M University, Galveston

Note: The actual survey was developed via Qualtrics and thus formatted differently.

In this first set of questions, you are asked to provide some basic information about your REU program.

1. What position do you hold in your REU program?
 - I do not run an REU program
 - Principal Investigator (PI)
 - Co-Principal Investigator (Co-PI)
 - Other (please elaborate): _____
2. About how many REU interns do you annually host? _____
3. What kind of internship experiences do you typically provide? (Select all that apply)
 - Computational
 - Field-based
 - Lab-based
 - Other (please elaborate): _____
4. How did you run your program this past year?
 - In person
 - Virtually
 - Hybrid (in person and virtually)
 - Cancelled

In this next set of questions, you are asked about your student recruitment and application experiences during the past year.

5. Approximately how many student applications did you receive? _____
6. How does the number of student applications that you received this year compare to those received on average pre-pandemic?
 - A lot more (over 50% more)
 - More (under 50% more)
 - About the same
 - Less (under 50% less)
 - A lot less (over 50% less)
 - Unsure
 - Not applicable
7. Did you notice any demographic shifts (e.g., in race/ethnicity, gender, student classification, low income) in this year's applicants, as compared to pre-pandemic years? If yes, please elaborate. _____

8. How many students declined participating in your REU program after having accepted?

9. What reasons did the student(s) give for pulling out? (Select all that apply)

- Concerns about potential Covid-19 infection
- Sick with Covid-19
- Family member needed assistance
- Anxiety or other mental health issues
- Chose a different internship opportunity
- Needed to keep their job(s)
- Other (please elaborate): _____

10. Please describe any observations that you made about which students withdrew after accepting the offer (e.g., who pulled out and who stayed). Was there a pattern?

In this last set of questions, you are asked about experiences running your REU program during the past year.

11. How much did Covid-19 affect the following elements of your REU program?

	None at all	A little	A moderate amount	A lot	A great deal
Participation of students	<input type="radio"/>				
Having to move to hybrid/online	<input type="radio"/>				
Mentor-mentee expectations	<input type="radio"/>				
Communication with students	<input type="radio"/>				
Supervision of students	<input type="radio"/>				
Cohort bonds	<input type="radio"/>				
Networking	<input type="radio"/>				

12. To help us understand how Covid-19 affected your REU program this year, please elaborate on your responses to the previous question. _____

13. Please indicate if you used any of the below strategies or techniques to enhance student experiences. (Select all that apply)

- Social media platforms (e.g., Slack, GroupMe)
- Frequent one-on-one student meetings
- GEO REU summer professional development workshops
- Paired group work
- Structured social activities
- Unstructured workspaces

14. Were there any techniques or strategies not listed above that you utilized to enhance student experiences? If so, what were they and were they successful?

15. At your home institution, did you have problems accessing any of the following support services? (Select all that apply)

- Business or financial support
- Covid-19 guidance or support
- Food services
- Housing accommodations
- Student health services
- Technical support
- Other (please elaborate): _____

16. Please state your level of agreement with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
I believe that student online experiences were as rewarding as if they had been in person	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe that MY online experiences were as rewarding as if they had been in person	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I believe that students would have preferred in-person experiences, if given the option

17. Overall, how satisfied were you with how your REU program ran?

- Extremely dissatisfied
- Somewhat dissatisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- Somewhat satisfied
- Extremely satisfied

18. Is there anything else that you would like to share about your experiences running your REU program this year? _____